

PERFORMANCE OF VARIOUS DESIGNS OF HYBRID LOOP- LOADED CFRP-TITANIUM STRAPS

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ABSTRACT

Loop-loaded straps are capable of transmitting high tensile loads using lightweight materials like CFRP. Additionally, these loops have the benefit to implement metallic components to reduce wear between the CFRP and the connecting part.

This paper investigates loop-loaded CFRP straps which integrate titanium parts into a Resin Transfer Molding process. On the textile side, preforms are manufactured by winding and by Tailored Fiber Placement. On the metal side, parts had been manufactured by Laser Additive Melting. Two metallic parts made of Ti-6Al-4V have been manufactured. The first metallic part is a hull which is placed at the one end of the CFRP strap to connect the strap to the testing machine. On the other end of the strap a titanium insert element was integrated to simulate a flange connection. Furthermore, different designs for this insert have been chosen, varying in radius and the quantity of the loops. The influence on the tensile strength depending on the design of the inserts has been tested using a tensile testing machine.

The strap specimens with different cores had been manufactured and examined using a tensile test. From these test results an insight into the influences of the flange design on the mechanical tensile properties as well as failure mechanisms of the hybrid strap were determined evaluated.

Hereby, it could be shown that cascaded cores provide an increased tensile strength of 5 % compared to a standard loop strap. Furthermore, different core radii have an influence regarding the tensile strength of nearly 20 % of hybrid loop-loaded straps. Finally, a crossed loop was tested with only 25 % fiber rovings like the other specimens but with a 50 % higher UTS compared to the highest UTS of a cascaded specimen.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reduction of weight is a challenging topic in nearly every industry which has to deal with mobile systems. In the aviation and in the automobile industry, less weight leads to reduced fuel consumption as well as reduced emissions. Therefore, fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) have been developed and became a popular material for these industries because FRP's offer a low specific density combined

with a high orthotropic strength. Structures which are able to transfer high tensile loads are straps. To support the FRP lateral in the vertex area of the strap a metallic insert can be integrated into the strap design to increase the overall performance [1]. Till now simple geometries have been used to reduce the effort of the manufacturing of these inserts. Using new technologies like the Additive Manufacturing Processes it is possible to manufacture complex design geometries which are able fulfil the demands of CFRP straps. Therefore, new design variations of the insert can be developed for hybrid loop-loaded straps.

In this study, hybrid loop-loaded straps consist of a FRP strap and two metallic elements. One of these elements is a hull which is required for connection to the testing machine. The second element has various designs and simulates a flange to connect hybrid straps to other parts.

Carbon is a suitable fiber material for straps. When fibers lay in unidirectional direction, Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has a great potential for high transfer loads. At the same time, CFRP is a lightweight material and contains a low density which is beneficial for lightweight applications.

The inserts have been generated using a titanium alloy and using Additive Manufacturing (AM), which improves the geometric design freedom compared to conventional processes. Therefore, different geometries of the metal part could be manufactured which consist out of a bearing and lateral supporting areas for the CFRP. Due to the direct bearing of the CFRP on these inserts, a titanium alloy has been chosen to reduce the discrepancies of the mechanical and electrochemical properties.

To investigate the influence of different loop-loaded strap designs and quantify their tensile performance, five designs have been developed which can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Investigated hybrid loop-loaded straps

2 MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

As mentioned, hybrid specimens have been manufactured integrating titanium inserts into the FRP. It seems really advantageous for loop applications which also transfer high loads. Titanium has also suitable properties for this application. First, it has a lower density than other metals like steel. Second, it implies a lower electrochemical potential difference to carbon than most other metals which leads to a reduced speed of corrosion. Examples of hybrid interfaces with a titanium transition area were examined by a previous study [2]. The manufacturing of those metallic parts is described in more detail in the following subchapter.

2.1 Insert manufacturing

To provide small batches of inserts with a high geometrical degree of freedom Laser Additive Manufacturing (LAM) has been chosen. Hereby a single LAM-machine with identical process parameters was used. The used machine is commercially available and contains a LAM-system with 200 W laser power, a layer thickness of 30 μm and an energy density of 45.3 J/mm^3 . The melting process takes place under inert atmosphere using an argon floated building chamber. In this process the parts have been generated layerwise using Ti-6Al-4V powder. Caused by the temperature gradient from more than 2000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is needed to melt the Ti-6Al-4V powder completely and high cooling rates support structures are needed to guarantee homogeneous heat dissipation. For this reason a lattice structure has been chosen which has to be removed after a relaxation heat-treatment for 3h at 650 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in argon with subsequent argon cooling. As the lattice structure grows into the generated part, manual removing leads to material residues at the supported surfaces. Those residues are minimized using abrasive and shot blasting for the whole part but leave a badly defined surface. That is why the cringles have been placed in a way that no support structures have been generated on surfaces which have a posterior interface to the CFRP.

For the examination five different designs have been chosen as well as one supportive hull. The designs can be seen in Figure 2. The first three designs are provided to examine simple loop designs and their influence of the radius (Fig. 2a/b). Figure 2c shows a cascaded cringle which is made of an extended semicircle (Part I) and an inlaying (Part II) fixed by 2 bolts. The last design, shown in Figure 2d, is leant on a hull. The subtle distinction of the geometry can be seen at the bearing area of the CFRP which integrates a supportive outlet for the CFRP.

Figure 2: LAM-generated cringles

2.2 CFRP

Essentially, CFRP consists of carbon fiber and resin. The used Carbon fiber have been supplied by TohoTenax and is distributed under the Name HTS40 F13 and provides 12.000 filaments which have a linear mass density of 800 tex. Those carbon fibers have a high tenacity and reach a tensile strength of 4300 MPa and a young modulus of 240 GPa. The fracture strain of the fiber is 1.8 %. The density of the fiber is 1.77 g/cm^3 .

Specimens made by Tailored Fiber Placement consist of a semi finished textile, a non-crimp fabric which is combined with endless fiber rovings. The non-crimp fabric with the identification code S37CX000 is supplied by the company Saertex. Tenax STS fibers are used in this textile and it

consists of a basis weight of 218 g/m². The endless fiber rovings of the specimen made by Tailored Fiber Placement are the same like in the winded specimens.

In addition to the carbon fibers, an epoxy resin system is used. The epoxy resin is called RTM6 and is supplied by the company Hexcel Composites. This commercially available resin is usually applied in composite structures in the aviation industry. The uncured resin has a density of 1.11 g/cm³ at 25 °C and the cured resin has a density of 1.14 g/cm³ at 25 °C. The young modulus of the resin is 2890 MPa. Hexcel Composites approved two different cure cycles which can be chosen by the operator [3]. The chosen cure cycle in this case will be shown in chapter 3.2 where the resin transfer molding process is briefly explained.

3 MANUFACTURING OF THE SPECIMENS

In this study, specimens were manufactured in two steps. In the first step, preforming was realized. This is necessary to fix the shape of the textile which is needed to enable an easy handling. When preforming has been finished, preforms were put in a mold and the resin was injected. After injection has been done, the resin was cured under temperature and the specimen was removed from the mold.

3.1 Preforming

After developing various hybrid loop-loaded straps, two different methods have been chosen to manufacture the preforms. The winding process has been selected for specimens M1 to M4 where parallel loops were manufactured. This method is optimal for tensile loaded straps. The Tailored Fiber Placement technology has been chosen for specimen M5 which is a suitable technology to create crossed loops. Both technologies are explained in the next chapters.

3.1.1 Winding

Like it is mentioned before, the winding technique is suitable especially for parallel loops like specimen M1 to M4. For the winding itself a preforming appliance was developed and manufactured. A schematic picture can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Scheme of the developed winding appliance

First, a reel with carbon fiber rovings on the one side and a preload system in the middle of the appliance was integrated. With this application, our preloading unit allows preloads between 10 N and almost 50 N. A preload of 10 N is necessary to create a winding pressure on the winding unit and therefore it ensured that upper fiber rovings fixed lower roving on the molding core. Over a preload of 50 N, fiber rovings showed fiber fractures shortly behind the reel. In this investigation, a preload of 25 N with the assumption of frictionless surface of the pulleys was used.

In the end of the appliance, the winding unit can be fixed with the titanium elements on both ends. This winding unit is the inner core of the mold at the same time. Between the carbon reel and the winding unit were pulleys which guaranteed a straight lead of the fibers and low fiber fractures.

In this study, a fiber volume content of 60 % was reached which implicates 32 windings of the carbon fiber material. The cross section of a winded specimen is 4 mm x 6 mm. The ultimate length of the loop-loaded strap was 255 mm.

3.1.2 Tailored Fiber Placement

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) is a method which is very useful when complicated structures of composites are asked. The biggest advantage of the Tailored Fiber Placement process is the high degree of automation which allows the operator to lay down endless fiber rovings to nearly any direction and fix them with a polyethylene terephthalate fiber. This ensures that fiber rovings cannot move transfer loads straight to the structure.

In this study, fiber rovings were laid down on the presented biaxial non-crimp carbon fiber fabric with an orientation of $+45^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}$. Loop structures are useful for tensile forces but are weaker for transverse loadings [4]. Therefore, it was used an orientation of $+45^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}$ to transfer transverse loads in the unidirectional CFRP at the edges.

The length of the specimen was also 255 mm and had an I-profile which is shown with its dimensions in Figure 4. In the middle of the specimen, four layers of non-crimp fabric were placed. On each side, four times fiber rovings were laid down on the non-crimp fabric to fasten the hull.

Figure 4: Cross section of a specimen made by Tailored Fiber Placement

A finished preform provided with TFP before cutting is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Preform before cutting made by a Tailored Fiber Placement process

Subsequently, the manufactured preform was cut along the outer contours and the inner circle. Then, the preform was pushed around the hull. Finally, the preform was ready to put in the mold.

3.2 Resin Transfer Molding

Specimens were manufactured in a RTM process. Therefore, mold is under vacuum and the resin was injected. Like described previously, the supplier of the resin approved two different curing cycles. Cycle no.2 was chosen which prescribes a curing temperature of 180 °C for 90 min during a resin temperature of 80°C and a mold temperature of 120 °C.

A representative description of the time-referenced heat increasing of the RTM process is shown in Figure 6. This temperature profile was recorded by a temperature logger which receives the data of the temperature within an interval of 60 min.

Figure 6: Core temperature of the mold during heat up and cool down

In the end, specimens were demolded. Figure 7, 8 and 9 show representative examples of manufactured specimens.

Figure 7: Manufactured specimen M1

Figure 8: Representative examples of winded loop-loaded straps with various designs

Figure 9: Close up of the I-profile of an injected Tailored Fiber Placement specimen M5

4 TESTING

Testing was done by the Z250 supplied by Zwick Roell and was based on DIN EN 2561. A preload was set at 20 N. Testing speed was set at 2 mm/min and clamping pressure for the test equipments were set at 200 bar. Specimen made by Tailored Fiber Placement had been prepared with cap stripes on the end of CFRP to transfer the load of the testing machine into the specimen. Therefore, clamping pressure of this specimen was 130 bar. Additionally, clip-ons were fastened at the specimens to register strains of the specimens and examine the young modulus. The young modulus shows no abnormalities and gets no further view in this study.

To investigate the tensile strength of the loop-loaded straps, special test equipment was manufactured, which has the potential of integrating every strap design as well as to arrange that the hybrid loop-loaded straps can be tested without lateral support like Figure 10 shows.

Figure 10: Close up of a specimen in test equipment without lateral support

Five specimens of design M1 was chosen and manufactured to get a standard deviation of hybrid loop-loaded strap tensile testing. Furthermore, three specimens of flange design M3 and two specimens of the cascaded flange design M4 were manufactured. Just one specimen of flange design M2 was tested. Moreover, one specimen which was manufactured with the Tailored Fiber Placement technology M5 was tested. This specimen will get a special view on.

Every specimen has been tested until fiber failure was occurred. Fiber failure is the ultimate tensile strength at the same time.

5 RESULTS

First, the results of specimens M1 are shown in Figure 11. The average of the test consists of a force of failure of 39.42 kN. The weakest specimen reaches a force of failure of 35.35 kN. However, the strongest specimen is specimen M1-5 with a force of failure of 42.64 kN. The standard deviation is 2963.57 N. Therefore, the uncertainty of the tests is 7.5 %.

Figure 11: Results of tensile test with loop-loaded strap design M1

Next, specimens of design M2 - M5 were tested. The average results are shown in Figure 12. Best results are noticed for specimens with cascades. Here, it was noticed that the strongest specimen reaches a force of failure of 43.19 kN. The other specimen reaches 39.73 kN. Specimen M2 is superior to specimens of design M3 regarding forces of failure. Specimen M2 has a maximum force of

37.17 kN and the average force is 33.37 kN. The specimen made by Tailored Fiber Placement fails at a force of 21.88 kN.

Figure 12: Average tensile loads of all tested specimens

Winded specimens show a very similar failing behavior independent from the shape (Figure 13). While increasing the load, first acoustic failure in the specimens occur around 10 kN regularly until the total failure point. This is caused by delamination and inter-fiber failures. These failure mechanisms do not directly lead to a total failure of the hybrid loop-loaded straps. Here, fiber failure leads to total failure in the specimens. The total fiber failure was localized in the transition area where CFRP leaves the titanium flange element. Before the total failure occurred, partially fiber failure has been detected which are the reason for load drops one or two times in the specimens. In hybrid loop-loaded straps with a cascaded flange design, these load drops occur three or four times. Additionally, in specimens with a cascade there was a further failure area at the CFRP which was positioned on the titanium hull on the other side.

Figure 13: Representative total failure of a specimen M1

Specimens manufactured by Tailored Fiber Placement showed another fracture behavior (Figure 14). Hereby, a first delamination or inter-fiber failures occur around 4 kN. Total failure occurred suddenly in the crossing area. Every specimen total failure was placed in the CFRP. The titanium elements have not damaged.

Figure 14: Failure in crossed Tailored Fiber Placement specimen M5

6 EXPLANATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Specimens of the semicircle flange design M1 show in comparison to specimens with smaller radius better results regarding the load of failure. Hereby, load introduction through the pin works steadily because of an equal pin load transfer to the whole titanium hull. The uncertainty is 7.5 % within this testing run.

Furthermore, the specimen of design M2 has a higher tensile strength than specimen M3 (Figure 15). Due to the fact that specimen M3 (7.5 mm) has a bigger loop radius than M2 (5.0 mm) this results have not been expected. A explanation for this tensile behavior can be found by the reason of the low quantity of specimens with design M2. It is probable that this high tensile strength of M2 is just an extraordinary statistical outlier. Therefore it is necessary to expand the tested quantity.

Figure 15: Results of the specimens M1, M2 and M3 regarding die CFRP radius

From all examined specimens the cascade design shows the highest tensile load capacity. This is caused by the relation between inner and outer radius which is significant to the performance of straps [5]. Another advantage of loop-loaded straps with cascades is the influence of the load of failure. The cascaded loop-loaded straps have a 5 % higher tensile strength than loop-loaded straps with design M1. These results were also predicted in the literature [1]. However, cascades weigh 16 g and consist of the highest weight of all flange designs. Regarding a semicircle core which weighs 3 g, cascades consist of a five times higher weight.

Specimens with a semicircle M1 reached 95.1 % of the ultimate tensile strength of cascaded specimens M4. Then, there are the two cringle designs M2 and M3 with lesser CFRP radii. First, the specimen of the design M2 with a CFRP radius of 5 mm shows a tensile performance of 89.6 % and then, specimens of M3 follows with a tensile performance of 80.5 % of the cascaded specimens.

Nearly every tested specimen which was manufactured in a winding process failed in the transition area of the CFRP strap and the titanium insert. Two possible explanations are conceivable in this case. Either the stiff titanium leads to a high notch effect in the CFRP or high differences in strains exist in the transition zone which is responsible for the failure area.

The specimen which is made by Tailored Fiber Placement failed approximately at 52.8 % regarding the strongest specimens which have been made by winding. Four additional layers of biaxial non crimp fabric transfer loads to the opposite strap which is act positively on the structure. But decisively, we integrated just a quarter of unidirectional endless carbon fiber rovings because positioning of less fibers with Tailored Fiber Placement ensures a more stabilized process which had a high priority. This leads to unidirectional fiber volume content in the straps of 45 %. In the next step, more fiber rovings will be integrated in this structure.

All in all, it is important to think about the flange design of hybrid loop-loaded straps to connect them with another part because the tensile performance of straps varies by the different load introduction method.

7 SUMMARY

In this study, several loop-loaded straps were developed to investigate their influences on the tensile performance. These loop-loaded straps consisted of a CFRP strap and two titanium elements which are made by LAM on both ends to simulate pin and flange connection. The preforms of the specimens were manufactured by winding or Tailored Fiber Placement. The injection was done in a Resin Transfer Molding process.

The different hybrid loop-loaded straps were tested with special test equipment in a Zwick Roell Z350 tensile testing machine. The forces of failure of every specimen was recorded and compared. It was noticed that cascades with two successively positioned loops offer the highest ultimate strength which occurred by 41.46 kN. Specimens with a semicircle reach the second best values of 39.42 kN. Specimens of two kind of cringles like in specimens M2 and M3 consist of a lesser ultimate tensile strength. The potential of a crossed hybrid loop-loaded strap have been shown. With this method where we used non-crimp fabrics and only 25 % of fiber rovings in comparison of the winded specimens, it was reached 52.8 % of the ultimate tensile strength of the highest UTS of a cascaded specimen. Furthermore, crossed straps are superior to parallel loops when transverse loads are asked which was not viewed.

These tests showed that hybrid loop-loaded straps are advantageous to transfer high loads. We have also showed some possibilities how to design loop-loaded straps. The design of the hybrid loop-loaded strap especially in the connecting area has a significant effect on the ultimate tensile strength of these straps. Therefore, it is important for the designer to know about these effects and the possibilities to design straps.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Schürmann, *Konstruieren mit Faser-Kunststoff-Verbunden*, Second Edition Springer Verlag, Heidelberg, 2007.
- [2] P. Schiebel, A. Lang, A. S. Herrmann, *Bauweisen für CFK-Aluminium-Übergangsstrukturen im Leichtbau*, *Proceedings of 18th Symposium Verbundwerkstoffe und Werkstoffverbunde, Chemnitz, Germany, March 30 - April 01, 2011*, Eigenverlag Chemnitz, Band 21, 2011, pp. 393-398.
- [3] Hexcel Corporation, *HexFlow RTM6 Product Data*, Published on December 2014.
- [4] A. Puck, *Einführen in das Gestalten und Dimensionieren*, *Kunststoff-Berater*, Supplement: *Konstruieren und Berechnen von GFK-Teilen*, 1969, pp. 44-66.
- [5] H. Conen, *Deformation und Versagen von GFK-Strangschlaufen*, *Kunststoffe*, Vol. 56, Book 9, 1966, pp. 629-631.